

Preliminary checklist of Boletales s. str. in Bulgaria

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Abstract. The paper provides a preliminary checklist of Boletales in Bulgaria. It includes 77 species belonging to 18 genera. For each recorded taxon the distribution throughout the country, references to literature sources as well as the collection in which herbarium specimens are kept are given.

Key words: Basidiomycetes, Boletales, Bulgaria, checklist, fungal diversity

Introduction

Basidiomycetes in Bulgaria are still poorly known. During the last few years national checklists were published for other Balkan countries – Greece (Zervakis *et al.* 1998), Turkey (Sesli & Baydar 1996), and Croatia (Mešić & Tkalčec 2002, 2003; Tkalčec & Mešić 2002, 2003a, b). There are no checklists available for Bulgaria up to date. The aim of this paper is to summarize the existing information about the species diversity and the distribution throughout the country of the species belonging to the order Boletales.

Materials and Methods

The checklist summarizes the information about the boletes from Bulgaria. It includes all the data, found in the available mycological literature up to date, as well as data arising from the holdings of the Mycological Collection of the Institute of Botany, Sofia (SOMF). In addition, some unpublished records, results of the senior author's field studies, are also included. Voucher specimens supporting these records are kept in SOMF.

When compiling the checklist, the system of the families and genera within the order is used as proposed by Kirk *et al.* (2001), but this paper includes only families of Boletales with tubular and lamellate hymenophore, viz. Boletaceae, Gomphidiaceae, Gyroporaceae, Hygrophoropsidaceae, Paxillaceae, and Suillaceae. The other families of Boletales

s. lat. are not included in that checklist. Species concept is accepted as follows: *Boletus* (incl. *Xerocomus*) – after Engel *et al.* (1983, 1996); *Boletellus* and *Suillus* – after Engel *et al.* (1996); *Rubinoletus* and *Buchwaldoboletus* – after Pilat & Dermek (1974); *Leccinum* – after Lannoy & Estadès (1995, 2001); *Gyrodon*, *Pulveroboletus*, *Chalciporus*, *Strobilomyces*, *Tylopilus* (incl. *Porphyrellus*), *Paxillus*, *Tapinella*, *Hygrophoropsis*, *Chroogomphus*, and *Gomphidius* – after Breitenbach &

Fig. 1. Map of the floristic regions of Bulgaria
 1. Black Sea coast, 2. Northeastern Bulgaria, 3. Danubian Plain, 4. Forebalkan, 5. Stara Planina Mts, 6. Sofia region, 7. Znepole region, 8. Vitosha Mt, 9. West Frontier Mts, 10. Valley of Strouma River, 11. Belasitsa Mt, 12. Slavyanka Mt, 13. Valley of River Mesta, 14. Pirin Mts, 15. Rila Mts, 16. Sredna Gora Mts, 17. Rhodopi Mts, 18. Thracian Plain, 19. Toundzha hilly region, 20. Strandzha Mt

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Kränzlin (1991). In addition, for some species the works of Singer (1965, 1967), Watling (1970), Engel (1983), Alessio (1985), and Galli (1998) were also consulted.

The distribution of the species throughout the country follows the phytogeographic division of Bulgaria proposed in Jordanov (1966) (Fig. 1).

Using the checklist one should once again be warned about its preliminary character. It has to be stressed that the contributions to the Bulgarian boletes with few exceptions usually do not provide information about the macro- and micromorphological features of the findings. Absolutely the same means for the specimens kept in the Mycological Collection (SOMF). This way it is very difficult to prove the proper determination of the older findings.

Marks and abbreviations used: Syn. – a synonym; ? – instead of an author name means that the author was not found in the available literature.

Survey of taxa

Boletaceae

Boletellus Murrill

B. pruvinatus (Fr. & Hök) Klofac & Krisai f. *pruvinatus*, Österr. Z. Pilzk. 1: 43, 1992.

Syn.: *Boletus pruvinatus* Fr. (*); *Xerocomus pruvinatus* (Fr.) Quél. (**)
Stara Planina Mts – central (Barsakov 1926a*; Fakirova *et al.* 2002**) Vitosha region (Barsakov 1928*)

B. pruvinatus f. *luteocarnosus* Klofac & Krisai, Österr. Z. Pilzk. 1: 43, 1992.

Syn.: *Xerocomus fragilipes* (C. Martin) Pouzar (*); *Boletellus fragilipes* (C. Martin) Kuthan (**)
Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989**) Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000*)

Boletus L.

B. aereus Bull. : Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 393, 1821.

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Forebalkan – eastern (Assyov 2004)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva 2002)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1961; SOMF)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 1997a; Gyosheva & Gussev 1998)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Strouma Valley – southern (Assyov, unpubl.)

Rhodopi Mts – central (Stoichev 1982) – without details (Hinkova *et al.* 1983)

Strandzha Mts (Hinkova 1965; Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

B. aestivalis Paulet ex Fr., Epicr. Syst. Mycol., p. 422, 1838.

Syn.: *Boletus reticulatus* Schaeff. ex Boud. (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Assyov 2004) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000)

Sofia region (Assyov 2004)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 1997a*; Gyosheva & Gussev 1998)

Vitosha region (Assyov 2004)

West Frontier Mts (Assyov 2004)

Belasitsa Mt (Assyov, unpubl.)

Rila Mts (Gyosheva 2003; Assyov, unpubl.)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Assyov 2004)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

B. appendiculatus (Schaeff. ex Fr.) Secr., Mycogr. Suisse 3: 34, 1833.

Syn.: *Boletus buxus* Rostk. (*); *B. obsonium* var. *buxus* (Rostk.) ? (**)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Forebalkan – eastern (Assyov 2004)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 1997a; Gyosheva & Gussev 1998; SOMF)

Vitosha region (Barsakov 1926a**, 1933*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Mihov 1994; SOMF)

Toundzha hilly region (Bogoev *et al.* 1993)

Strandzha Mt (SOMF)

B. armeniacus Quél., Ann. Sci. Nat. Bordx. S.-O., Mém. 2: 42, 1884.

Syn.: *Xerocomus armeniacus* (Quél.) Quél. (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989*)

Vitosha region (Denchev, unpubl.; Assyov, unpubl.)

Thracian plain (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987*)

Bulgaria – without details (Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995*)

B. badius Fr. : Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 515, 1821.

Syn.: *Xerocomus badius* (Fr. : Fr.) E.-J. Gilbert (*)

Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980*) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000*)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926b)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a; Assyov, unpubl.)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a*, b*; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000*; SOMF*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Mihov 1994*)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Assyov 2004; SOMF*) – central (SOMF*)

B. calopus Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 390, 1821.

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

- Sofia region (Hinkova 1961; SOMF)
 Znepole region (Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; SOMF)
 Vitoshka region (Assyov 2004)
 Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)
 Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a; Gyosheva 2003; Assyov, unpubl.)
 Sredna Gora Mts – western (Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)
 Rhodopi Mts – western (Hinkova *et al.* 1979; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF) – central (Hinkova *et al.* 1979)
- B. caucasicus** Singer ex Alessio, Boletus, p. 175, 1985.
 Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)
- B. chrysensteron** Bull., Herb. Fr., p. 328, 1791.
 Syn.: *Xerocomus chrysensteron* (Bull.) Quél. (*)
 Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*; SOMF*)
 Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962*; Stoichev & Dimcheva 1984*)
 Forebalkan – western (SOMF*)
 Stara Planina Mts – western (Barsakov 1926b; Hinkova & Droumeva 1978*) – central (Vanev & Reid 1986; Fakirova *et al.* 2002*) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980*; Boeva 2002*)
 Sofia region (Hinkova 1950; SOMF*)
 Znepole region (Gyosheva 1997a*; Gyosheva & Gushev 1998*)
 Vitoshka region (Pilát 1926; Barsakov 1933, 1936; Hinkova 1954; Kreisel 1959)
 Pirin Mts – northern (Droumeva-Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993*; SOMF*)
 Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928; Hinkova 1958a*; Kreisel 1959*; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000*; Gyosheva 2003*; SOMF*)
 Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970*; Vulchev *et al.* 2000*)
 Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1926a; Gyosheva 1998*; SOMF*) – central (Gyosheva 1996*; SOMF*)
 Toundzha hilly region (Bogoev *et al.* 1993*)
 Bulgaria – without details (Engel *et al.* 1996*)
- B. dupainii** Boud., Bull. Soc. Mycol. France 18: 139, 1902.
 Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Boeva 2002)
- B. edulis** Bull. : Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 392, 1821.
 Forebalkan – eastern (SOMF)
 Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; SOMF) – central (Barsakov 1926a; Fakirova *et al.* 2000, 2002) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva 2002)
 Sofia region (SOMF)
 Znepole region (Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1984; Gyosheva 1994; Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; Gyosheva & Gushev 1998; SOMF)
- Vitoshka region (Barsakov 1926a, 1928, 1933; Hinkova 1954; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)
 Pirin Mts – northern (Droumeva-Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)
 Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928; Hinkova 1958a; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Gyosheva 1997b, 2003; Assyov, unpubl.)
 Sredna Gora Mts – western (Barsakov 1930; Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; Vulchev *et al.* 2000; SOMF)
 Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1928, 1931; Gyosheva 1998; Assyov, unpubl.) – central (Gyosheva & Zaimova 1996)
- B. erythropus** (Fr. : Fr.) Krombh., Consp. Fung. Esc., p. 24, 1821.
 Syn.: *Boletus erythropus* (Fr. : Fr.) Krombh. subsp. *erythropus* (*)
 Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981*, 1989*)
 Stara Planina Mts – central (Vanev & Reid 1986; Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva 2002; SOMF)
 Znepole region (Hinkova 1965; Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1984, Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; Gyosheva 1997a; Gyosheva & Gushev 1998; SOMF)
 Vitoshka region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a)
 Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)
 Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Gyosheva 2003; Assyov, unpubl.)
 Sredna Gora Mts – western (Mihov 1994; SOMF)
 Rodopi Mts – western (Assyov 2004; SOMF) – central (Stoichev 1982; SOMF) – eastern (SOMF)
 Strandzha Mt (Hinkova 1965; SOMF)
- B. fechtneri** Velen., Česke Houby 4-5: 704, 1922.
 Forebalkan – eastern (Assyov 2004)
 Znepole region (Gyosheva 1994; Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994)
 Rhodopi Mts – western (SOMF) – central (Hinkova *et al.* 1979)
- B. ferrugineus** Schaeff., Fung. Bav. 4: 85, 1774.
 Syn.: *Xerocomus spadiceus* (Fr.) Quél. (*)
 Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978*; SOMF*) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000*) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980*)
 Sofia region (SOMF*)
 Pirin Mts – northern (Droumeva-Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993*)
 Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970*; SOMF*) – eastern (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1984*; SOMF*)
 Rhodopi Mts – central (SOMF*) – eastern (SOMF*)
- B. gabretae** Pilát, Česká Mykol. 22: 167, 1968.
 Stara Planina Mts – western (Vanev & Reid 1986)

B. impolitus Fr., Epicr. Syst. Mycol., p. 421, 1838.

Syn.: *Boletus obsonium* Fr. (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962; Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989; SOMF)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Boeva 2002)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 1994, 1997; Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; SOMF)

Vitoshka region (Barsakov 1933*; Hinkova 1961)

Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (Hinkova *et al.* 1979; SOMF)

Toundzha Hilly region (SOMF)

B. junquilleus (Quél.) Boud., Icon. Mycol. 4: 76, 1910.

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981)

B. kuthanii Assyov & Denchev, Mycotaxon 90: in press, 2004.

Syn.: *Xerocomus flavus* Kuthan & Singer (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*; BRA*)

B. lanatus Rostk. in Sturm, Deutsch. Fl. Pilze 3: 77, 1844.

Syn.: *Xerocomus lanatus* (Rostk.) Singer (*); *X. spadiceus* auct. (**) non *X. spadiceus* (Fr.) Singer

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981**, 1989*)

B. lupinus Fr., Epicr. Syst. Mycol., p. 418, 1838.

Znepole region (Hinkova & Stoichev 1983; SOMF)

B. luridus Schaeff. : Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 391, 1821.

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; SOMF) – central (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1982; Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989; Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Boeva 2002, Assyov 2004)

Znepole region (Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1984; Gyosheva 1994, 1997; Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; Gyosheva & Gushev 1998; SOMF)

Vitoshka region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a; Assyov, unpubl.)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, Gyosheva 2003)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1928, 1931) – eastern (SOMF)

Thracian Plain (SOMF)

Annotation. Engel *et al.* (1983) reported from Bulgaria var. *erythroteron* (Bezděk) Pilát & Dermek (Hrib. Huby,

p. 123, 1974) (*comb. inval.*, ICBN, Art. 33.3). Despite of the fact that this combination was never validly published, there are other nomenclatural problems connected with this name. When publishing *Boletus 'erythroteron'* [sic] Bezděk provided just a short diagnosis in Czech, which contains information only about the color of the flesh and its changes. He does not give any indication that the species is close to *B. luridus*. This way it is very difficult to guess why Pilát & Dermek refer the species of Bezděk as variety of the former. Until more specimens are collected, this taxon is better considered as doubtful.

B. moravicus Vacek, Studia Bot. Čechosl. 7: 36, 1946.

Syn.: *Xerocomus moravicus* (Vacek) Herink (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981*; Assyov, unpubl.)

B. parasiticus Bull. : Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 389, 1821.

Syn.: *Xerocomus parasiticus* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél.

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*)

B. pinophilus Pilát & Dermek, Česká Mykol. 27(1): 6, 1973.

Syn.: *Boletus edulis* Bull. var. *pinicola* Vittad. (*); *B. pinicola* (Vittad.) A. Venturi (**)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Boeva 2002)

Vitoshka region (Hinkova 1954*; Assyov, unpubl.)

Pirin Mts – northern (Droumeva-Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993; Assyov, unpubl.)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a*; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Assyov, unpubl.)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Assyov 2004) – central (Stoichev 1982**, SOMF**)

B. porosporus Imler ex G. Moreno & Bon, Doc. Mycol. 7(27-28): 6, 1977.

Syn.: *Xerocomus porosporus* (Imler ex G. Moreno & Bon) Contu (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*)

Znepole region (Gyosheva & Gushev 1998*)

B. pulverulentus Opat., Arch. Naturgesch. 2: 27, 1836.

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962)

Vitoshka region (Assyov 2004)

Strandzha Mt (SOMF)

B. queletii Schulzer s. lat., Hedwigia 24: 143, 1885.

Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962; SOMF)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000)

Znepole region (SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (SOMF) – southern (Hinkova 1965)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (SOMF)

B. queletii* var. *queletii

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989; Assyov, unpubl.)

Forebalkan – eastern (Assyov 2004)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Vitosha region (Assyov 2004)

Bulgaria – without details (Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995)

Annotation. For the taxonomy of *B. queletii* see Alessio (1985), Heykoop (1995), and Lannoy & Estadès (2001).

***B. queletii* var. *discolor* (Quél.) Alessio, Boletus, p. 193, 1985.**

Syn.: *Boletus erythropus* (Fr. : Fr.) Krombh. subsp. *discolor* (Quél.) Dermek, Kuthan & Singer (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989*)

Bulgaria – without details (Engel *et al.* 1983*; Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995)

***B. queletii* var. *lateritius* (Bres. & Schulzer) E.-J. Gillbert, Les Bolets, p. 118, 1931.**

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

***B. radicans* Pers. : Fr., Syst. Mycol. 1: 390, 1821.**

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980)

Znepole region (SOMF)

Sredna Gora Mts – eastern (SOMF)

***B. regius* Krombh., Nat. Abb. Schw. 2: 3, 1832.**

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Assyov 2004) – central (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1982; Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Znepole region (Gyosheva & Gushev 1998; SOMF)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a)

Belasitsa Mt (Assyov, unpubl.)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (SOMF)

***B. rhodopurpureus* Smotl., Čas. Českosl. Houbařu 29: 31, 1952.**

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (SOMF)

Toundzha Hilly region (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987)

Bulgaria – without details (Engel *et al.* 1983; Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995)

***B. rhodoxanthus* (Krombh.) Kallenb., Z. Pilzk. 5: 31, 1925.**

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989)

Stara Planina Mts – western (SOMF)

West Frontier Mts (Assyov 2004)

Rila Mts (Assyov 2004)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (SOMF)

***B. rubellus* Krombh., Nat. Abb. Schw. 5: 12, 1836.**

Syn.: *Xerocomus rubellus* (Krombh.) Quél. (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981*, 1989*)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000*) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980*; SOMF*)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 1997a*; Gyosheva & Gushev 1998*)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958b; SOMF)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970*; SOMF*)

Thracian Plain (SOMF*)

Bulgaria – without details (Engel *et al.* 1996*)

***B. satanas* Lenz, Schwämme, p. 67, 1831.**

Stara Planina Mts – western (Barsakov 1926b) – central (Barsakov 1926a) – eastern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989; Boeva 2002; Assyov 2004)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 1997a; SOMF)

Vitosha region (Barsakov 1933)

Rila Mts (Georgiev 1906; Barsakov 1926a, 1928; Hinkova 1958a; SOMF)

***B. speciosus* Frost, Bull. Buffalo Soc. Nat. Sci. 2: 101, 1874.**

Syn.: *Boletus pseudoregius* Huber ex Estadès (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, as *B. appendiculatus* Secr., 1989*)

Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (SOMF)

Annotation. Kuthan & Kotlaba (1981) reported under the name *B. appendiculatus* a single found with redish pileus and bluing flesh and pores. Later, Kuthan & Kotlaba (1989) identified this specimen with *B. pseudoregius*. Some modern authors (e.g., Galli 1998; Lannoy & Estadès 2001) consider that *B. pseudoregius* is not conspecific with *B. speciosus* and the last name was missapplied by some European mycologists. Since this species is known to us only by the dried samples kept in SOMF, here we prefer to keep the name *B. speciosus* following Singer (1967), Pilát & Dermek (1974), Engel *et al.* (1983), and Breitenbach & Kränzlin (1991), although later it might be proved that the Bulgarian specimens are not identical with the American fungus.

***B. splendidus* C. Martin subsp. *splendidus*, Bull. Soc. Bot. Genève 7: 190, 1894.**

Syn.: *Boletus legaliae* Pilát ex Pilát (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989; Assyov, unpubl.)

Znepole region (SOMF)

Bulgaria – without details (Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995*)

B. subtomentosus L. : Fr., Sist. Mycol. 1: 389, 1821.

Syn.: *Xerocomus subtomentosus* (L. : Fr.) Quél. (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (SOMF*)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962*; SOMF*)

Forebalkan – western (SOMF*)

Stara Planina Mts – western (SOMF*) – central (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – eastern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*; Boeva 2002*)

Znepole region (Gyosheva & Gushev 1998*)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a, b; SOMF*)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1955b)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987*)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a*, b*; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000*; Gyosheva 2003*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970*)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Gyosheva 1998*; SOMF*) – central (Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000*) – eastern (SOMF*)

Bulgaria – without details (Engel *et al.* 1996*)

B. torosus Fr. in Fr. & Hök, Boleti, p. 10, 1836.

Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1928)

B. truncatus (Singer, Snell & E.A. Dick) Pouzar, Česká Mykol. 20: 2, 1966.

Syn.: *Xerocomus truncatus* Singer, Snell & E.A. Dick (*)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970*; SOMF*)

Buchwaldoboletus Pilát

B. lignicola (Kallenb.) Pilát, Friesia 9(1-2): 217, 1969.

Syn.: *Pulveroboletus lignicola* (Kallenb.) Pilát (*)

Rhodopi Mts – central (Stoichev 1982*)

Chalciporus Bat.

C. piperatus (Bull. : Fr.) Bat., Bolets, p. 19, 1908.

Syn.: *Boletus piperatus* Bull. : Fr. (*); *Suillus piperatus* (Bull. : Fr.) Kuntze (**)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova 1965**, SOMF**)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954*; Gyosheva & Bogoev 1985; SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (Droumeva-Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993*; SOMF)

Rila Mts (Georgiev 1906*; Barsakov 1926a*; Hinkova 1958a**, Gyosheva 1997b*; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000*; SOMF*)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1931*; Vanev & Reid 1986**, Gyosheva 1998*; SOMF) – central (Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000*; SOMF**)

Leccinum Gray

L. aurantiacum (Bull.) Gray, Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 1: 646, 1821.

Syn.: *Boletus scaber* var. *aurantius* (Sow.) ? (*)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1961; SOMF)

Vitosha Mt (Barsakov 1926a*; SOMF)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – central (Stoichev 1982)

Strandzha Mt (SOMF)

L. carpini (Schulzer) M.M. Moser ex D.A. Reid, Trans. Brit. Mycol. Soc. 48: 525, 1965.

Syn.: *Leccinum griseum* (Quél.) Singer (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981*, 1989) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981*, 1989)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova 1962)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978*; SOMF*) – central (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1982*; Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980*; Boeva 2002, 2002*; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF*)

Sofia region (SOMF*)

Znepole region (Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1984*; Gyosheva 1994*, 1997; Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994*; SOMF*)

Vitosha region (Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF*)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970*; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF*)

Rhodopi Mts – western (SOMF*) – central (Stoichev 1982*; SOMF*)

Strandzha Mt (SOMF*)

L. crocipodium (Letell.) Watling, Trans. Bot. Soc. Edinburgh 39(2): 200, 1961.

Boletus rimosus Venturi (*); *Leccinum nigrescens* (Richon & Roze) Singer (**); *L. tessellatus* (Gill.) ? (***)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989**) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989**, Assyov, unpubl.)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989**) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980***)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1961**)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954*, 1955a*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – eastern (SOMF)

Thracian Plain (Stoichev 1982**)

Strandzha Mt (Hinkova 1965**)

Bulgaria – without details (Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995; Lannoy & Estadès 1995)

L. duriusculus (Schulzer) Singer, Amer. Midl. Naturalist 37(1): 122, 1947.

Syn.: *Boletus duriusculus* Schulzer (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Forebalkan – western (Barsakov 1926b*)

Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987)

Rhodopi Mts – central (SOMF)

Thracian Plain (Stoichev 1982)

L. quercinum Pilát ex Pilát in Pilát & Dermek, Hrib. Huby, p. 151, 1974.

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987; Mihov, 1994; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Toundzha Hilly region (Gyosheva & Droumeva-Dimcheva 1991)

L. roseotinctum Watling, Notes Roy. Bot. Gard. Edinburgh 29: 267, 1969.

Syn.: *L. percandidum* (Vassilkov) Watling (*)

Rila Mts (Vanev & Reid 1986*)

Annotation. *Boletus percandidus* Vassilkov was published without a Latin diagnosis and therefore the combination based on that name, *Leccinum percandidum* (Vassilkov) Watling, is illegitimate. For further nomenclatural details about *L. percandidum* see Lannoy & Estadès (1995).

L. scabrum (Bull. : Fr.) Gray, Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 1: 647, 1821.

Syn.: *Boletus scaber* Bull. : Fr. (*)

Forebalkan – western (SOMF)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva 2002)

Vitosha region (Pilát 1926*; Barsakov 1926a*, 1928*, 1933*; Hinkova 1954*; SOMF)

Rila Mts (Georgiev 1906*, Barsakov 1926a*; Hinkova 1958a; Gyosheva 2003)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Mihov 1994)

Rhodopi Mts – western (SOMF) – central (SOMF)

L. versipelle (Fr.) Snell, Lloydia 7(1): 58, 1944.

Syn.: *Boletus versipellis* Fr. (*); *Leccinum testaceoscabrum* (Secr.) Singer (**)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954*)

Rila Mts (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987**)

Phylloporus Quél.

P. pelletieri (Lév.) Quél., Fl. Mycol. Fr., p. 409, 1888.

Syn.: *Phylloporus rhodoxanthus* (Schwein. : Fr.) Bres. (*); *Paxillus paradoxus* Kalchbr. (**)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1933**)

Znepole region (Gyosheva 2000)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Stoichev 1981)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987*)

Pulveroboletus Murrill

P. gentilis (Quél.) Singer, Amer. Midl. Naturalist 37: 17, 1947.

Syn.: *Aureoboletus gentilis* (Quél.) Pouzar (*); *Pulveroboletus cramesinus* (Secr.) Singer (**)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989*) – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970**)

Strobilomyces Berk.

S. strobilaceus (Scop. : Fr.) Berk., J. Bot. (Hooker) 3: 77, 1851.

Syn.: *Boletus strobilaceus* Scop. : Fr. (*); *Strobilomyces floccopus* (Vahl : Fr.) Karst. (**)

Stara Planina Mts – western (SOMF) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000; SOMF)

Sofia region (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1982**; SOMF**)

Vitosha Mt (Hinkova 1954, 1955a; Assyov 2004; SOMF**)

West Frontier Mts (Assyov 2004)

Pirin Mts – southern (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1988**; SOMF**)

Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928*; Gyosheva 2003; Assyov, unpubl.)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (SOMF, SOMF**)

Rhodopi Mts – western (SOMF**)

Tylopilus Karst.

T. felleus (Bull. : Fr.) Karst., Rev. Mycol. 3: 16, 1881.

Rila Mts (SOMF)

T. pseudoscaber Secr. ex A.H. Smith et Thiers, Mycologia 60: 950, 1960.

Syn.: *Porphyrellus pseudoscaber* (Secr.) Singer (*); *P. porphyrosporus* (Fr.) E.-J. Gilbert (**)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987**)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987**; Assyov 2004; SOMF*) – without details (Dimcheva & Stoichev 1987*)

Rila Mts (Gyosheva 1997b**; Assyov 2004; SOMF**)

G o m p h i d i a c e a e

Chroogomphus (Singer) O.K. Miller

Ch. helveticus (Singer) M.M. Moser in Gams, Kl. Kryptogamenfl. Mitteleur., 3rd edn, II/b2, p. 51, 1967.

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt 1977; Dörfelt & Müsch 1987)

Rila Mts (Dörfelt 1977; Dörfelt & Müsch 1987; Vanev & Reid 1986; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Gyosheva 2003; SOMF)

Bulgaria – without details (Courtecuisse & Duhem 1995)

Ch. rutilus (Schaeff. : Fr.) O.K. Miller, *Mycologia* 54: 543, 1964.

Syn.: *Gomphidius rutilus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Lund. & Nannf. (*);
G. viscidus (L. : Fr.) Fr. (**)

- Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978)
Danube plain (Assyov 2004)
Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978;
SOMF) – central (Vanev & Reid 1986; Fakirova *et al.*
2000) – eastern (SOMF)
Znepole region (Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1984; Gyosheva &
Vassilev 1994; SOMF)
Vitoshka Mt (Pilát 1926**); Hinkova 1954**; Gyosheva &
Bogoev 1985; SOMF)
West Frontier Mts (Assyov 2004)
Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987*; Droumeva-
Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993)
Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928**; Hinkova 1958a; Kreisel
1959; Gyosheva 1997b; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000;
SOMF)
Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970;
SOMF)
Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1939**; SOMF) –
central (Gyosheva & Zaimova, 1996; Gyosheva &
Andreeva 2000; SOMF) – eastern (SOMF)

Gomphidius Fr.

G. glutinosus (Schaeff. : Fr.) Fr., *Epicr. Syst. Mycol.*, p. 319, 1838.

- Northeastern Bulgaria (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978)
Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva
1978) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern
(Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva 2002)
Vitoshka Mt (Hinkova 1954; SOMF)
Pirin Mts – northern (Barsakov 1928; SOMF)
Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928; Hinkova 1958a; Gyosheva
1997b; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000)
Sredna Gora Mts – western (Mihov 1994)
Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1931; Vanev & Reid
1986; Gyosheva 1998; SOMF) – central (Gyosheva
& Zaimova, 1996; Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000;
SOMF)

G. maculatus Fr., *Epicr. Syst. Mycol.*, p. 319, 1838.

- Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2002)
Vitoshka Mt (Barsakov 1933)

G. roseus (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet, *Champ. Fr.*, p. 623, 1878.

- Rila Mts (Gyosheva 1997b; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000;
Assyov 2004; SOMF)
Rhodopi Mts – central (Klika 1926)

Gyroporaceae

Gyroporus Quéll.

G. castaneus (Bull. : Fr.) Quéll., *Enchir.*, p. 161, 1886.

Syn.: *Suillus castaneus* (Bull. : Fr.) Karst. (*)

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981,
1989)

Northeastern Bulgaria (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern
(Boeva 2002; Assyov 2004)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1950*)

Vitoshka region (Hinkova 1954; 1955a*; Assyov, unpubl.;
SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (SOMF)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b; Assyov, unpubl.)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970;
Mihov 1994; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – central (Stoichev 1982)

G. cyanescens (Bull. : Fr.) Quéll., *Enchir.*, p. 161, 1886.

Stara Planina Mts – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000; SOMF) –
eastern (Boeva 2002)

Vitoshka Mt (Hinkova 1954; Kreisel 1959; Assyov,
unpubl.; SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987; Droumeva-
Dimcheva & Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1993)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Rhodopi – central (Stoichev 1982; SOMF) – eastern
(SOMF)

Rubinoboletus Pilát & Dermek

R. rubinus (W.G. Sm.) Pilát & Dermek, *Česká Mykol.* 23(2):
81, 1969.

Syn.: *Chalciporus rubinus* (W.G. Sm.) Singer (*); *Boletus
rubinus* W.G. Sm. (**)

Sredna Gora Mts – eastern (Stoichev & Dimcheva
1987*)

Annotation. This only record was erroneously referred to
the Black Sea coast by Gyosheva *et al.* (2000**).

Hygrophoropsidaceae

Hygrophoropsis (J. Schröt.) Maire ex Martin-Sans

H. aurantiaca (Wulfen : Fr.) Maire, *L'Empoissement*, p. 99,
1921.

Syn.: *Cantharellus aurantiacus* Wulfen : Fr. (*)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Barsakov 1926b*)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1950*; SOMF)

Znepole region (Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994)

Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928*; Hinkova 1958a; Gyosheva &
Denchev 2000; Gyosheva 2003)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1936*)

Bulgaria – locality indet. (Klika 1926*)

H. morgani (Peck) Bigelow, *Nova Hedwigia Beih.* 51: 66,
1975.

Syn.: *Cantharellus olidus* Quéll. (*); *Hygrophoropsis olida*
(Quéll.) Métrod (**)

Vitoshka Mt (Hinkova 1954*; 1955a*)

Strouma Valley – southern (Dimcheva *et al.* 1992;
SOMF**)

Tapinella E.-J. Gilbert

T. panuoides (Fr. : Fr.) E.-J. Gilbert, Bolets, p. 68, 1931.

Syn.: *Paxillus panuoides* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. (*)

Rila Mts (Rosnev & Stoichev 1985*; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000*; SOMF*)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (SOMF*)

Rhodopi Mts – central (SOMF*)

Paxillaceae

Gyrodon Opat.

G. lividus (Bull. : Fr.) Sacc., Syll. Fung. 6: 52, 1888.

Black Sea coast – northern (Hinkova 1961; SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (Hinkova 1965)

Paxillus Fr.

P. atrotomentosus (Batsch : Fr.) Fr., Epicr. Syst. Mycol., p. 317, 1838.

Stara Planina Mts – eastern (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; Boeva 2002)

Sofia region (Hinkova 1950)

Vitosha region (Pilát 1926; Hinkova 1954)

Rila Mts (Rosnev & Stoichev 1985; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Assyov, unpubl.)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1929; SOMF) – central (Gyosheva & Zaimova, 1996; Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000; SOMF)

P. filamentosus Fr., Epicr. Syst. Mycol., p. 317, 1838.

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; SOMF)

P. involutus (Batsch : Fr.) Fr., Epicr. Syst. Mycol., p. 317, 1838.

Black Sea coast – southern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989)

Danube plain (SOMF)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926c; Hinkova 1965; Assyov, unpubl.)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; SOMF) – central (Fakirova *et al.* 2000) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989; Boeva 2002; SOMF)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a)

Znepole region (Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; SOMF)

Strouma Valley – southern (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1982)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Gyosheva 2003)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Gyosheva 1998) – central (SOMF)

Thracian plain (Stoichev 1982; SOMF)

Suillaceae

Suillus Adans.

S. bovinus (L. : Fr.) Roussel, Fl. Calvados, p. 34, 1796.

Syn.: *Boletus bovinus* L. : Fr. (*); *B. bovinus* var. *mitis* (Krombh.) Quél. (**)

Forebalkan – eastern (Barsakov 1926a*)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova 1965; Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; SOMF) – central (Barsakov 1926a*) – eastern (Boeva 2002)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926a*)

Vitosha Mt (Barsakov 1926a**, 1928*, 1933*; SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (Barsakov 1928*)

Rila Mts (Georgiev 1906*; Barsakov 1926a*, 1928*; Gyosheva 1997b, 2003; Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Barsakov 1930*; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1928*; SOMF) – central (Pilát 1937*; Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000; SOMF) – eastern (SOMF)

S. collinitus (Fr.) Kuntze, Rev. Gen. Pl. 3(2): 536, 1898.

Sofia region (Assyov 2004)

Thracian Plain (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987; SOMF)

S. flavidus (Fr. : Fr.) J.C. Presl, Vseobecny Rostlinopis 2: 1917, 1846.

Rila Mts (Gyosheva & Denchev 2000)

S. granulatus (L. : Fr.) Roussel, Fl. Calvados, p. 34, 1796.

Syn.: *Boletus granulatus* L. : Fr. (*)

Black Sea coast – northern (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989)

Danube Plain (SOMF)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; SOMF; SOMF*) – central (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1989) – eastern (Hinkova & Droumeva 1978; Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva 2002; SOMF)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926a*)

Znepole region (Gyosheva-Bogoeva 1984; Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994; SOMF)

Vitosha Mt (Barsakov 1933*; Hinkova 1954*)

Pirin Mts – northern (Assyov, unpubl.) – without details (Pilát 1937*)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b; Gyosheva 1997b; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970; Assyov, unpubl.)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1926a) – central (Hinkova 1950; Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000)

Rhodopi Mts – without details (Hinkova *et al.* 1983)

S. grevillei (Klotzsch) Singer, Farlowia 2: 259, 1945.

Syn.: *Boletus elegans* Schum. : Fr. (*); *B. flavus* With. (**)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926a**)

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954*)

Pirin Mts – northern (SOMF) – without details (Dimcheva & Stoichev 1987)

Rila Mts (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1984; Assyov 2004)
Bulgaria – without details (Engel *et al.* 1996)

S. luteus (L. : Fr.) Roussel, Fl. Calvados, 1st edn, p. 34, 1796.

Syn.: *Boletus luteus* L. : Fr. (*)

Danube Plain (SOMF)

Sofia region (SOMF)

Znepole region (Gyosheva & Vassilev 1994)

Vitosha region (Barsakov 1930*, 1933*; Hinkova 1954*;
SOMF; SOMF*)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Barsakov 1930*; Hinkova
& Droumeva 1978; SOMF) – central (Fakirova *et al.*
2000) – eastern (Droumeva & Stoichev 1980; Boeva
2002)

Pirin Mts – northern (Vanev & Reid 1986*) – southern
(SOMF) – without details (Pilát 1937*)

Rila Mts (Hinkova 1958a, b; Gyosheva 1997b, 2003;
Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Hinkova & Fakirova 1970)

Rhodopi Mts – western (Barsakov 1931*; SOMF) –
central (Gyosheva & Zaimova 1996; Gyosheva &
Andreeva 2000; SOMF) – without details (Hinkova
et al. 1983)

S. sibiricus (Singer) Singer, s. lat., Farlowia 2: 260, 1945.

Pirin Mts – northern (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987; Dörfelt
& Müsch 1987; Droumeva-Dimcheva & Gyosheva-
Bogoeva 1993; SOMF) – without details (Dimcheva
& Stoichev 1987)

Rila Mts (Stoichev & Dimcheva 1987; Gyosheva 2003)

S. sibiricus subsp. *helveticus* Singer, Lilloa 22: 657, 1951
[1949] (*nom. illeg.*).

Pirin Mts – northern (Assyov 2004)

Annotation. For more detailed comments on this taxon
reffer to Redeihl & Simonini (1998).

S. variegatus (Schwartz : Fr.) Richon & Roze, Atlas Champ.,
p. 178, 1888.

Syn.: *Boletus variegatus* Schwartz : Fr. (*)

Stara Planina Mts – western (Hinkova & Droumeva
1978; SOMF)

Vitosha region (Pilát 1926*; SOMF)

Pirin Mts – northern (Dörfelt & Müsch 1987; Assyov
2004)

Rila Mts (Gyosheva & Denchev 2000; SOMF)

Rhodopi Mts – western (SOMF) – central (Stoichev 1982;
Gyosheva & Andreeva 2000; Assyov, unpubl.; SOMF)

Uncertain taxa

Boletus edulis Bull. var. *reticulatus* Bull. ?

Vitosha region (Barsakov 1926a)

Annotation. It may be assumed that this record probably
might to be referred to *Boletus pinophilus*, as far as possible

to judge from the short description of the finding provided
by the author. Barsakov's specimen was not found in
SOMF to prove that possibility.

B. pachypus Fr.

Vitosha region (Hinkova 1954, 1955a)

Rila Mts (Barsakov 1928)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926a)

Annotation. The name *B. pachypus* has been interpreted in
different ways by various authors. It seems that Bulgarian
records under that name might refer to *B. calopus*, but
no specimens are available and no enough information is
provided in these publications, that could support that.

B. purpureus Fr.

Sredna Gora Mts – western (SOMF)

Annotation. The name *B. purpureus* was variously
interpreted by different authors. Further examination
both of fresh material and exsiccates is required.

B. scaber var. *niveus* (Fr.) ?

Sofia region (Barsakov 1926a)

Annotation. Barsakov used this name for a taxon of
Leccinum with a pale pileus. Numerous “white” species are
recognized within the genus nowadays (Lannoy & Estadès
1995) and it is impossible to refer this record to certain
currently accepted taxon.

B. umbrinus Pers.

Vitosha region (Barsakov 1933)

B. variegatus Schwartz f. *rugosa* Barsak., Izv. Bulg. Bot.
Druzh. 8: 101, 1939 (*nom. inval.*)

Sofia region (Barsakov 1939)

Xerocomus tessellatus (Letell.) Watling

Sredna Gora Mts – western (Mihov 1994)

Conclusions

The checklist includes totally 77 species belonging to 18 genera
and 6 families. Most of the species – 54, belong to Boletaceae.
The richest genera are *Boletus* with 37 species, *Leccinum* – 9,
and *Suillus* – 8. The remaining genera are presented with 5 or
less species (Tab. 1).

Distribution of the records throughout the country is
unequal. Greatest number of species is recorded from Stara
Planina Mts (44 species), Rhodopi (39), Rila Mts (39),
Vitosha region (36), the Black Sea coast (35), and Sredna
Gora Mts (35). No records are available from Mt Slavyanka
and the Valley of Mesta River.

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the Bulgarian National Scientific Fund.

Table 1. Distribution of the taxa of Boletales in Bulgaria by floristic regions

Regions	Boletaceae									Gomphidia-ceae			Gyro-poraceae		Hygrophoro-psidaceae			Paxillaceae			Suilla-ceae		Total species per region	
	<i>Boletellus</i>	<i>Boletus</i>	<i>Buchvaldoboletus</i>	<i>Chalciporus</i>	<i>Lecinum</i>	<i>Phylloporus</i>	<i>Pulveroboletus</i>	<i>Srotiolomyces</i>	<i>Tylopilus</i>	Total	<i>Chroogomphus</i>	<i>Gomphidius</i>	Total	<i>Gyroporus</i>	<i>Rubrioboletus</i>	Total	<i>Hygrophoropsis</i>	<i>Tapinella</i>	Total	<i>Gyrodon</i>	<i>Paxillus</i>	Total		<i>Suillus</i>
Black Sea Coast	1	25		3		1			30			0	1		1			0	1	1	2	1	1	35
northern	1	13		2		1			17			0			0			0	1		1	1	1	19
southern		23		3		1			27			0	1		1			0		1	1			29
Northeastern Bulgaria		9		1					10	1	1	2	1		1			0				0		13
Danube Plain									0	1		1			0			0		1	1	2	2	4
Forebalkan		7		2					9			0			0			0			0	1	1	10
western		2		2					4			0			0			0			0			4
eastern		5							5			0			0			0			0	1	1	6
Stara Planina Mts	1	23	1	4	1		1	1	32	1	2	3	2		2	1		1		2	2	4	4	44
western		10		1	2			1	14	1	1	2			0	1		1		1	1	4	4	22
central	1	18		3	1		1	1	25	1	2	3	2		2			0		1	1	3	3	34
eastern		16		4					20	1	1	2	2		2			0		2	2	3	3	29
Sofia region		7		4	1		1		13			0	1		1	1		1		2	2	5	5	22
Znepole region		19		1	1				21	1		1			0	1		1		1	1	2	2	26
Vitosha region	1	15	1	5			1		23	1	2	3	2		2	1		1		2	2	5	5	36
West Frontier Mts		2					1		3	1		1			0			0			0		0	4
Strouma Valley		1							1			0			0			1		1	1		0	3
northern									0			0			0			0			0		0	0
southern		1							1			0			0	1		1		1	1		0	3
Belasitsa Mt		2							2			0			0			0			0		0	2
Slavyanka Mt									0			0			0			0			0		0	0
Mesta Valley									0			0			0			0			0		0	0
Pirin Mts		9	1	1		1	1	1	13	2	1	3	2		2			0	1	1	2	6	6	26
northern		9	1	1			1	1	12	2	1	3	2		2			0	1	1	2	6	6	25
southern		1					1		2			0			0			0			0	1	1	3
Rila Mts		13	1	5		1	2	2	22	2	2	4	2		2	1	1	2		2	2	7	7	39
Sredna Gora Mts		19		5		1	1		26	1	1	2	1		1		1	1		2	2	3	3	35
western		18		5		1	1		25	1	1	2	1		1		1	1		2	2	3	3	34
eastern		2							2			0			0			0			0		0	2
Rhodopi Mts		18	1	1	5		1		26	1	2	3	2		2	1	1	2		2	2	4	4	39
western		11		1	2		1		15	1	1	2			0	1		1		2	2	4	4	24
central		10	1	1	4				16	1	2	3	2		2		1	1		2	2	4	4	28
eastern		9		1					10	1		1	1		1			0			0	1	1	13
Thracian Plain		2		2					4			0			0			0		1	1	1	1	6
Toundzha hilly region		3		1					4			0		1	1			0			0		0	5
Strandzha Mt		4		3					7			0			0			0			0		0	7
Total	1	37	1	1	9	1	1	1	2	54	2	3	5	2	1	3	2	1	3	1	3	4	8	8

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